

Impact of Screen Time on Cognitive Functioning, Discrimination, and Loneliness among Hearing-impaired Young Adults

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Hearing-impaired young adults depend on digital technology for social connectivity and networking, for instance, communicating through video conference or any related medium and for information and knowledge acquisition due to their biological (auditory) limitation. However, this leads to an increase in their time spend on screen that is screen time, which deteriorates their cognitive functioning and mental health. Therefore, the current paper aims to investigate the impact of screen time on cognitive functioning, mainly working memory and attention span, perceived discrimination, and loneliness among hearing-impaired young adults. The study was conducted on 115 hearing-impaired young adults who are admitted to different undergraduate courses in Misra Rehabilitation University, Lucknow, India, specifically dedicated to the special population. Everyday Discrimination scale was used for discrimination, De Jong Gierveld Scale for Loneliness, Corsi Bloc test for Working memory and Stroop task for attention span have been employed for the data collection. The collected data were analysed using relevant inferential statistics on SPSS v27.1. The results of the present papers illustrate the influential role of high screen time in impairing cognitive functioning skills, specifically low working memory capacity and attention span and in eliciting the feeling of discrimination, while low screen time impacts loneliness. Highlighting a bidirectional role of screen time in cognitive and psychosocial functioning among hearing-impaired young adults. The study suggests a need for preventive digital intervention for better well-being and cognitive functioning for hearing-impaired young adults.

Keywords: Screen time, executive functioning, loneliness, discrimination, and hearing impairment

Hearing impairment is a global issue affecting almost 430 million individuals, which is almost 20% of the world population and is expected to be as high as 700 million by 2050 (WHO, 2019). In India, as per the WHO reports and census data, 63 million people are suffering from some auditory impairment, which constitutes 6% of the Indian population (Varshney, 2016). Within this population, young adults face unique challenges in education, employment, communication and social integration (Arlinger, 2003; Wasim, 2024). Further, these challenges increase the risk of psychosocial issues such as loneliness and social isolation and often result in poorer cognitive functioning (Arlinger, 2003; Taljaard et al., 2015). However, to overcome these challenges, hearing-impaired young adults (HI-YA) depend upon electronic devices such as phones and laptops, which act as a compensatory tool for their auditory limitation (Soylemez et al., 2025; Van Wier et al., 2021). Video conferencing, instant messaging platforms, and social media have become an integral part, as these allow them to communicate, engage in academic activities and maintain social relationships that would

be inaccessible otherwise (Van Wier et al., 2021). Moreover, digital platforms give them a platform to interact, acquire knowledge and information, while offering them a visual text-based content, thereby enabling HI-YA to indulge more actively in the world predominantly designed for the hearing population (Soylemez et al., 2025).

Nonetheless, this digital dependence has influenced the screen time of HI-YA to high rates. Screen time (ST) can be explained as “the duration of screen use interaction, which includes both productive and leisure activities undertaken by an individual” (Orben, 2020). There is a prevalence of high screen time (HST) in young adults, ranging between 7 to 9 hours (Luo et al., 2025). In the case of HI-YA, this range is likely to be higher, given their digital dependence connected to their communication necessity and social survival (Vanderloo et al., 2025). In the literature, HST is linked with impairing cognitive functioning (Xiong et al., 2024) and mental health. Cognitive functioning is often referred to as Executive functioning (EF) in the literature. EF is a higher-order cognitive ability, a multidimensional construct that encompasses various interrelated cognitive capabilities (Banich, 2009). Among its multiple sub-constructs, working memory and attention are relevant in the present paper. Working memory (WM) is “a limited storage for manipulating information necessary for complex cognitive tasks such as learning, reasoning and comprehension” (Baddeley & Hitch, 1974). Attention Span is “the ability to concentrate/focus on a particular stimulus for a specific period of time” (Posner, 1980). WM and attention span are adversely affected by prolonged ST (Meda, 2025; Xiong et al., 2024). For HI-YA, this is primarily concerning, as any further deficiency in their EF due to HST can have a negative impact on their daily functioning, academic pursuits and overall well-being (Xiao et al., 2025).

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Beyond EF, the impact of ST on psychosocial functioning and mental health has been an area of interest in recent years. Specifically, loneliness and discrimination are more relevant to the HI-YA context. Loneliness is defined as the emotional or social discomfort of feeling alone (De Jong Gierveld & Van Tilburg, 2006) a significant psychosocial issue in HI-YA. Communication barriers and social exclusion in different settings increase the feelings of loneliness and social isolation in HI-YA (Baik & Kim, 2025; Shukla et al., 2020). Low screen time (LST) can disconnect them from their social network, thus intensifying the feelings of loneliness and isolation (Zhang et al., 2025). Meanwhile, discrimination is unfair treatment of an individual or a community based on different prejudicial factors and group membership (Williams et al., 1997). It is commonly experienced by HI-YA through social stigma and social exclusion (Guan et al., 2022). Their digital dependence and HST intensify their feelings of discrimination by making them experience the inaccessible online content, social comparison and dominance of the hearing population, serving as a constant reminder of their marginalized status (Vanderloo et al., 2025).

Complex Role of Screen Time in Hearing-impaired Young Adults

There is a bidirectional influence of ST in the context of HI-YA (Vanderloo et al., 2025). HST impairs EF by diminishing WM (Xiong et al., 2024) and reducing attention span (Meda, 2025) while amplifying discrimination in parallel, through increased exposure to an unjust digital environment (Vanderloo et al., 2025). However, LST exacerbates the feelings of loneliness by limiting their compensatory tools for social connectivity (Zhang et al., 2025). This bidirectional relationship leads HI-YA to be simultaneously harmed by HST (Xiao et al., 2025) and socially disadvantaged by LST, there by illustrating the complex role of ST in shaping their cognitive and psychological functioning and well-being (Oswald et al., 2020). Thus, understanding this complex role is vital for developing and implementing an intervention that will optimise the technological benefits while minimising its related harm for this vulnerable population.

Review of Literature

The present section highlights the research undertaken on the influence of ST on WM, attention span, or on EF collectively, discrimination and loneliness among HI-YA. A thorough and elaborate literature review was undertaken to develop a strong basis for the current study.

ST among young adults with different disabilities has been recognised as a public health concern, as this population has shown consistently elevated usage of devices. A systematic review and meta-analysis undertaken by Vanderloo et al. (2025) illustrates that this population has a daily ST ranging between 0.5 to 7.27 hours. Vanderloo et al. (2025) suggested that excessive screen use is a common issue among the disability groups, and limiting it is important to prevent the negative consequences. Further, the authors recommended the need for interventions and public health policies specially curated to address the unique ST pattern of disability population (Vanderloo et al., 2025).

Nagata et al. (2024) analysed the cohort data of 9538 adolescents and found that higher total ST leads to several mental health problems, such as depression, ADHD, conduct and somatic disorders. Screen types include texting, video chat, and games,

primarily associated with mental issues, suggesting that duration of ST as well as the nature of screen engagement also influence mental health.

Similarly, Xiao et al. (2025) investigated ST in the context of 24-hour movement behavior guidelines, which include increased physical activity, reduced ST and adequate sleep among children and adolescents with hearing loss. Upon investigating the data from the 2018-2022 National Survey of Children's Health, the authors found that adherence to ST guidelines is alarmingly low, as only 12.6% were complying with the guidelines. Further, when ST was reduced with physical activity and proper sleep, the participants demonstrated better emotional outcomes, for instance, less anxiety and depression reported. Thus, highlighting ST as a consequential behavior target for individuals with hearing loss (Xiao et al., 2025).

In a study of 570 Chinese Deaf and Hard of Hearing university (DHH) students, Guan et al. (2023) investigated the psychological pathways to Problematic Smartphone Use (PSU), a form of excessive and compulsive ST engagement. Findings suggested that perceived discrimination had a significant association with PSU. Moreover, a sense of security and social avoidance were found to mediate this relationship both independently and serially, implying that discrimination lowers the sense of security and increases the social avoidance, which consequently increases the ST to PSU levels. Therefore, HST in DHH students is a psychosocial response to exclusion and marginalisation (Guan et al., 2023).

A longitudinal nationally representative study was conducted by Zhang et al. (2022) investigating the role of video calling in reducing loneliness among adults with hearing impairment. The findings suggest that video calling reduces loneliness, serving as a meaningful buffer against social isolation, especially for hearing-impaired individuals.

A systematic review exploring the correlation between ST, language development and cognitive functioning was undertaken by Bal et al. (2024). The review integrated the results from 14 research papers and identified four themes for the aforementioned relationship, namely: screen content, passive and active ST, attentional problems and parent-child interaction. The results of the review suggest that excessive passive ST negatively impacts attention, memory and emotional regulation. Moreover, the prevalence of attentional issues is found to be associated with high ST exposure. Collectively, the review suggests that the impact of ST is not only dependent upon the time but also on the content type, interactivity and the context in which it occurs (Bal et al., 2024).

ST exposure among HI-YA has been studied in coherence with psychosocial issues. A Survey conducted by Xiong et al. (2024) found that smartphone addiction, excessive and uncontrolled ST engagement, mediated the relationship between executive dysfunction and anxiety. Moreover, academic procrastination moderated the relationship between smartphone addiction and anxiety, implying that problematic ST interacts with psychological distress. These findings suggest that problematic ST, such as smartphone addiction, is not just a communication compensatory tool but has serious mental health consequences. Thereby highlighting a need for intervention to address this issue as a medium through which academic and cognitive difficulties (academic procrastination & executive dysfunction) transcend into heightened anxiety in hearing impaired population.

Relevance of the Study

Notwithstanding the substantial evidence of the impact of ST on cognitive functioning, psychosocial and mental health, the literature is characterized by notable gaps. The majority of ST/phone usage/online presence studies have focused on the general or hearing population, with relatively limited studies studying disable population, for instance, hearing impairment in this context. Moreover, studies that considered the hearing-impaired population primarily explored either cognitive or psychosocial constructs, neglecting the interplay between ST, cognitive functioning, and psychosocial issues. Furthermore, the bidirectional nature of ST has rarely been explored in this context. The aforementioned gaps highlight the need for a comprehensive and integrated study into the complex and heterogeneous impact of ST on EF (attention span and WM), discrimination and loneliness among HI-YA.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the difference in working memory, attention span, discrimination and loneliness between individuals with high screen time and low screen time.
- To examine the relationship between screen time, working memory, attention span, discrimination and loneliness.
- To examine the impact of screen time on executive functioning (working memory & attention span).
- To examine the impact of screen time on psychosocial issues (discrimination & loneliness).

Method

Participants

The study population comprises 115 hearing-impaired young adults aged between 18 and 27 years (Mean age = 21 years). There were 63 males and 52 females admitted to different undergraduate courses in the Misra Rehabilitation University, India. Random sampling was employed, and participants were selected as per the inclusion criteria. Participants who can read and write, know and use Indian Sign Language, and are congenitally deaf are included in the study.

Research Design

The current study employed a correlational research design, which aims to examine the relationship and impact of ST on cognitive functioning (attention span & WM), discrimination and loneliness.

Measures

Socio-demographic Schedule: A basic socio-demographic information schedule was created by the author to collect all the necessary and related information related to the participants. The schedule includes information seeking on age, gender, education, area of living, number of siblings and birth order.

Screen Time Questionnaire by Vizcaino et al. (2019): A 18 item ST assessment was utilised to measure and quantify the use of commonly screen-based devices such as T.V, phone, laptop and video games. The questionnaire has demonstrated good to excellent reliability of 0.61 to 0.90 (Vizcaino et al., 2019). The questionnaire was utilized to divide the participants into two groups: LST (<10 hours of ST) and HST (>10 hours of ST) groups.

Everyday Discrimination Scale (EDS-9) by Williams et al. (1997):

This is a 9-item self-report inventory assessing the number of experiences and minor acts of discrimination has happened with an individual (Williams et al., 1997). EDS-9 (Williams et al., 1997) demonstrated good reliability and validity with an excellent internal reliability (Cronbach's Alpha of .88).

De Jong Gierveld Loneliness Scale by De Jong Gierveld and Van Tilburg (2006): It is a 6-item scale that measures two dimensions of loneliness, namely 'emotional loneliness' and 'social loneliness'. The subscales have proven to be valid and reliable as the scale has satisfactory Cronbach's alphas (α 0.85 and 0.79) and mean inter-item correlations (r 0.53 & 0.44) were found for the social and emotional loneliness scales, respectively (Pronk et al., 2011).

The Stroop Task for Attention by Stroop (1935): Participants were asked to respond to the name of the ink of the colour displayed on the screen, whilst ignoring the colour name originally written. For example, if the RED appears written in BLUE colour on the screen, the correct response would be BLUE as the ink colour is BLUE. In this example, the participants are required to inhibit the impulse to respond "RED". It signifies the cognitive focus of an individual as reading a word, which is an automatic semantic process, conflicts with the ink colour, which acts as a visual interference.

Corsi Block Test (CBT) for WM by Corsi (1972): The task consists of nine blocks positioned at random on the screen. The participant repeats the clicking order as presented. The number of blocks tapped in sequence starts with 2 blocks and increases with each correctly repeated sequence. The test concludes when the participant fails to reproduce a given sequence of taps. The longest sequence, called the Corsi span, will be noted. The average forward Corsi span for an adult ranges between five and seven blocks (Monaco et al., 2013).

Data Analysis

The collected data was analysed using the JAMOVI 2.5.6. To find the group differences between LST and HST, a t-test was employed. To examine the relationship between the variables, correlation analysis was undertaken. Further, a regression analysis was used to ascertain the impact of ST on WM, attention span and psychosocial issues.

Results

Table 1

Showing Group Differences between the LST and HST with Respect to Attention, Working Memory, Discrimination and Loneliness

	LST	HST	t(103)	p
	Mean & SD	Mean & SD		
Working Memory	4.41±1.27	3.08±.988	6.02	<.001
Attention	31.52±3.28	18.56±5.83	13.49	<.001
Loneliness	28.48±5.81	16.29±3.94	12.77	<.001
Discrimination	22.11±4.57	29.64±5.48	-7.50	<.001

Note. $p < .001$

The results showed a significant difference between the LST and HST participants on WM ($t = 6.02$, $<.001$), attention ($t = 13.49$, $<.001$), loneliness ($t = 12.77$, $<.001$), and discrimination ($t = 7.50$, $<.001$) as illustrated in Table 1. The LST group showed better WM ($M = 4.41$ & $M = 3.08$ for HST) and attention span ($M = 31.52$ & $M = 18.56$ for HST), illustrating better EF among the LST participants. However, the LST group ($M = 28.48$) showed higher loneliness

compared to the HST group ($M = 16.29$), confirming that screen-based interactions serve as a means for social connection for HI-YA. Further, HST participants reported higher discrimination ($M=29.64$ & $M = 22.11$ for LST), illustrating elevated ST associated with higher perceived discrimination.

Table 2

Showing Correlation between Screen Time, Attention, Working Memory, Discrimination and Loneliness

Variable	1	2	3	4	5
1. Working memory					
2. Loneliness	.458***				
3. Discrimination	-.210*	-.341***			
4. Attention	.549***	.636***	-.524***		
5. Screen time	-.510***	-.783***	.595***	-.799***	

Note. * $p < .05$, *** $p < .001$

Figure 1

Showing Correlation Matrix For Screen Time, Attention, Working Memory, Discrimination and Loneliness

The correlation analysis revealed that ST has a negative correlation with WM ($r = -.510, <.001$), attention span ($r = -.799, <.001$), and loneliness ($r = -.783, <.001$) as shown in Fig 1, illustrating an inverse relationship between EF skills and ST along with acting as a buffer against the feelings of loneliness (ST increases, loneliness decreases). However, it has a positive relationship with discrimination, signifying that higher ST will result in higher feelings of perceived discrimination. Other inter-variable correlations are shown in Table 2.

Table 3

Showing the Impact of Screen Time on Working Memory

Variables	95% CI		B	t	p
	SE	LB			
Screen time	.221	-1.77	-1.33	-6.02	.001**

Note. Dependent Variable = Working memory. $F(1,103) = 36.2^{**}, p < 0.001, R = .510$, SE = Standard error, CI= Confidence Interval for B, LB = Lower Bound, UB= Upper bound, B = Estimate, ***= $p < .001$

The regression model examining the impact of ST on WM was statistically significant ($F(1,103) = 36.2, < 0.001$), with ST explaining 26% of variance in WM ($R = .510, R^2 = .260$). Further,

the regression coefficient signifies ST as a significant negative predictor of WM ($B = -1.33, SE = .221, t = -6.02, <.001$) with 95% CI ranging between -1.77 to -.891 as shown in Table 3.

Table 4

Showing the Impact of Screen Time on Attention

Variables	95% CI		B	t	p	
	SE	LB				UB
Screen time	.961	-14.9	-11.1	-13.0	-13.5	.001**

Note. Dependent Variable = Attention. $F(1,103) = 182^{**}, p < 0.001, R = .799$, SE = Standard error, CI= Confidence Interval for B, LB = Lower Bound, UB= Upper bound, B = Estimate, ***= $p < .001$

The regression model examining the impact of ST on attention was statistically significant ($F(1,103) = 182, < 0.001$), with ST explaining 63.8% of variance in attention ($R = .799, R^2 = .638$). Further, the regression coefficient signifies ST as a significant negative predictor of attention ($B = -13.0, SE = .961, t = -13.5, <.001$) with 95% CI ranging between -14.9 to -11.1 as shown in Table 4. This signifies that HST results in a decrease of 13.0 units in attention span scores.

Table 5

Showing the Impact of Screen Time on Loneliness

Variables	95% CI		B	t	p	
	SE	LB				UB
Screen time	.955	-14.1	-10.3	-12.2	-12.8	.001**

Note. Dependent Variable = Loneliness. $F(1,103) = 163^{**}, p < 0.001, R = .783$, SE = Standard error, CI= Confidence Interval for B, LB = Lower Bound, UB= Upper bound, B = Estimate, ***= $p < .001$

Table 5 illustrates the regression model examining the impact of ST on loneliness, which was statistically significant ($F(1,103) = 163, < 0.001$), with ST explaining 61.3% of the variance in loneliness ($R = .783, R^2 = .613$). Further, the regression coefficient signifies ST as a significant negative predictor of loneliness ($B = -12.2, SE = .955, t = -12.8, <.001$) with 95% CI ranging between -14.1 to -10.3.

Table 6

Showing the Impact of Screen Time on Discrimination

Variables	95% CI		B	t	p	
	SE	LB				UB
Screen time	1.004	5.54	9.53	7.54	7.50	.001**

Note. Dependent Variable = Discrimination. $F(1,103) = 56.3^{**}, p < 0.001, R = .595$, SE = Standard error, CI= Confidence Interval for B, LB = Lower Bound, UB= Upper bound, B = Estimate, ***= $p < .001$

The regression model examining the impact of ST on discrimination was statistically significant ($F(1,103) = 56.3, < 0.001$), with ST explaining 35.4% of variance in perceived discrimination ($R = .595, R^2 = .354$). Further, the regression coefficient signifies ST as a significant positive predictor of perceived discrimination ($B = 7.54, SE = 1.004, t = 7.50, <.001$) with 95% CI ranging between 5.54 to 9.53 as shown in Table 6. This signifies that HST results in an increase of 7.54 units in feelings of perceived discrimination compared to LST.

Discussion

The present study aims to investigate the complex role of ST in the HI-YA population. The study highlights the group differences between the HST and LST groups with respect to WM, attention, loneliness and discrimination. Further, the study unravels the Impact of HST on WM, attention and discrimination, while acting as a buffer against the feelings of loneliness in HI-YA.

Screen Time and Working Memory

The findings of the study revealed that ST has a negative impact on WM while explaining 26% of its variance. Further, the HST group has shown poor WM capacity compared to the LST. HST is often characterised by multitasking, application hopping, and exposure to infinite pieces of information (Dobransky & Hargittai, 2016) which collectively pressure and overload the limited capacity of the WM system. Constantly, this overload decreases the storage capacity of WM and its information manipulation capability, thus weakening the WM performance (Paas & Van Merriënboer, 2020). The HI population depends heavily on visual WM for processing and comprehending information in both academic and social life (Rudner et al., 2016). Further deterioration in WM due to HST has compounded adverse effects for the HI-YA population in terms of academic performance, learning efficiency and daily functioning (Kronenberger et al., 2018).

Screen Time and Attention Span

There is a negative association between ST and attention span, explaining 63.8% variance in attention scores by ST exposure in the present study. Similar to WM, the HST group has a lower attention span than the LST group. These findings are supported by cognitive overload theory, which proposes that the constant and stimulating nature of digital content overloads the cognitive processes, thereby shortening the selective and sustained attention capacity (Paas & Van Merriënboer, 2020; Skulmowski & Xu, 2021). Moreover, the arousal hypothesis states that intensified arousal is elicited by prolonged ST and interferes with attentional capacities (Martella et al., 2020). The rapid, fragmented digital content fires the sympathetic nervous system to produce a state of hyperarousal, which is contradictory to calm, focused attention required for cognitive and academic-related tasks (Unsworth & Robison, 2017).

Screen Time and Loneliness

The general population literature proposes that HST is linked with increased loneliness (Matthews et al., 2025) on the contrary, the current findings highlight that HST decreases loneliness. The findings are aligned with the Social compensation hypothesis, which posits that the individual indulges in digital activities (HST) to compensate for physical social interaction, resulting in lower feelings of loneliness (Dorrestein et al., 2025; Ma et al., 2023). For HI-YA, digital dependence isn't optional, but rather a compensatory tool that serves as a primary channel for social communication, building and maintaining relationships and social engagement (Orben, 2020). Consequently, LST damages this compensatory tool, thereby disconnecting the HI-YA from their social network, which then results in feelings of loneliness (Movallali et al., 2018). The results of the current study highlight a key difference between the normal hearing population and the hearing-impaired population. LST may increase the social well-being of the normal hearing

population (Santos et al., 2024) but the same LST for HI-YA exacerbate their loneliness, as for them, digital connectivity is synonymous with social survival (Liu, 2025; Movallali et al., 2018).

Screen Time and Discrimination

There is a significant positive impact of ST on discrimination, accounting for 35.4% variance in discrimination scores among HI-YA. The HST group reported substantially higher discrimination scores compared to the LST group. The Online Disinhibition Effect (Suler, 2004) explains the theoretical framework for explaining the HST association with increased feelings of perceived discrimination. Unambiguous social cues and perceived anonymity in a digital environment make prejudiced attitudes elicit freely exposing HST users to increased frequency of discriminatory content and interactions. Additionally, the instances of cyberbullying and the lack of deaf-friendly digital spaces further contribute to the feelings of discrimination among HI-YA with HST (Saunders, 2016). The study emphasises the need for more inclusive digital design, accessible online content and deaf friendly spaces that can reduce the discriminatory experience of HI-YA in the digital environment (Dobransky & Hargittai, 2016).

Conclusion

The study examines the interplay of ST, cognitive and psychosocial functioning among HI-YA. Simultaneously investigating the impact of ST on cognitive functioning (WM & attention span) and psychosocial constructs (loneliness & discrimination) within a single framework, and by demonstrating the bidirectional nature of these effects. The present study presents an integrated understanding that advances theoretical understanding and practical application. The findings are vital for the HI-YA across educational and cultural settings who navigate the same paradox of digital dependence and its related consequences. In conclusion, ST is neither beneficial nor detrimental for HI-YA. Its impact is complex, bidirectional, and deeply intertwined with the social reality of hearing impairment. The solution isn't a technological or digital restriction, but in optimising its use, creating an equitable digital environment and empowering HI-YA with cognitive and psychosocial tools to navigate the digital world in a manner that enhances rather than undermines their digital and overall well-being.

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